
D.4.1.2 Report on the connection of CARE WP4 activity with the databases and initiatives already in place

Workpackage 4

Responsible Partner: ANSES

Contributing partners: RIVM

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<table style="width: 100%; border: none;"> <tr> <td>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td>OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td>ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other</td> <td>international</td> <td>stakeholder(s):</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">.....</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Social Media:</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Other recipient(s):</td> </tr> </table>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/>	OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/>	Project Management Team <input type="checkbox"/>		Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/>	Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/>		National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/>			EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		Other	international	stakeholder(s):			Social Media:			Other recipient(s):		
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REPORT ON THE CONNECTION OF CARE WP4 ACTIVITY WITH THE DATABASES AND INITIATIVES ALREADY IN PLACE

This document gathered the interaction CARE project established with stakeholders (ECDC and EFSA) as well as other EJP OH projects.

A. Interaction with ECDC

Date: September 7, 2021

Location: Videoconference

Participants:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Johanna Takkinen; ECDC - Ursula Gonzales Barron; IPB - Vasco Cadavez; IPB - Eric Evers; RIVM 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Anne Thebault; Anses - Pauline Kooh; Anses - Juliana De Oliveira Mota; Anses - Laurent Guillier; Anses
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Discussions:

Session	Discussion
Presentation of One Health EJP CARE project Objectives and focus on WP4 <i>Laurent Guillier</i>	Need to build a reference material database of strains present in food allowing comparing and predicting. Reflection on which strains should be considered subtyped. It would be wise to take advantage of official samples in order to enrich the database. (ex. To use RASFF – the Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed)
Findings from the European survey Identification of (meta-)data from QMRA studies <i>Juliana De Oliveira Mota</i>	Discussions took place around the theme: “what can be done to increase the sharing and the accessibility to high quality knowledge?” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Common platform to share models and data, such as RAKIP platform is a good initiative but needs many human and financial resources. It must be an integral platform where the user is a win-win - A QMRA group should be created in Europe: EFSA organizes a data collection network and a QMRA theme should be proposed. Update: CARE project and WP4 work will be presented in the next meeting (October 5 and/or 6, 2021) - Challenge : Translation of the different methodologies and data sources at national level - Data collection: member states should invest in the investigation of strains/subtyping because there is a lack of information about distribution of hazards in food - A spreadsheet about subtypes should be created to list the state of knowledge and to encourage investments - Example of work to be promoted: Joint ECDC, EFSA and EURL Lm report: European Listeria typing exercise (ELiTE) from ECDC, EFSA and EURL, 2021. - The virulence of the hazards are often considered but there is a lack of counts, except for Listeria monocytogenes. This
Identification of European initiatives for knowledge sharing <i>Laurent Guillier and Juliana De Oliveira Mota</i>	

	<p>procedure must be promoted, particularly in the RASFF, because it is one of the important factors of virulence.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - However all the initiatives are time consuming and need economical resources
<p>Focus on Pathogens-In-Foods project <i>Ursula Gonzales Barron</i></p>	<p>Participants acknowledged the major interest of the Pathogens-In-Foods project in data identification and share.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The access to the information depends of the level of the user (Basic, Advanced...) and this depends on the involvement of the user on the sharing of the knowledge. - Information about the food hazards (subtyping type, the sampling strategies and the methods of analysis for example) can be downloaded in a csv file. - All the data comes from literature papers. - Importance of the origin of sampling: the country of the data information (country of publication) was not always the country of sampling - The use of RASFF data, if the hazards in food would be analyzed (ex. subtyping), would benefit this initiative because the origin of the food product is always mentioned.

B.Interactions with EFSA

Date: October, 5 2021

Location: Videoconference

Participants:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EFSA BIOCONTAM Unit: Maria Teresa Da Silva Felicio, Beatriz Guerra Roman, Michaela Hempen, Maria Francesca Iulietto, Ernesto Liebana, Winy Messens, Pietro Stella - CARE project: Laurent Guillier, Juliana de Oliveira Mota <p>MRA Network</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Austria: Monika Matt - Belgium: Lieven De Zutter, Kim Feys, Elie De Boeck - Bulgaria: Hristo Najdenski, Dora Petlova - Croatia: Brigita Hengl, Jasenka Petric - Cyprus: Christos Kourtis - Czechia: Veronika Vlasakova, Zuzana Ileninová 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Estonia: Mati Roasto - Finland: Jukka Ranta - France: Pauline Kooh, - Germany: Anja Buschulte - Greece: Panagiota Gousia - Hungary: Zsuzsanna Sréterné Lancz, David Toldi - Ireland: Mary Lenahan - Italy: Maria Elisabetta De Angelis - Lithuania: Indre Stoskuviene - Netherlands : Aarieke de Jong, Linda Verhoef - Poland : Elzbieta Mackiw - Portugal : Manuela de Sol - Romania : Laurentiu Ciupescu - Slovakia : Lubomír Valík - Spain : Elena Carrasco Jimenez, Antonio Valero Diaz - Sweden: Jakob Ottoson Norway Danica Grahek-Ogden - Switzerland: Francoise Fridez
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Discussions:

Session	Discussion
<p>Presentation of One Health EJP CARE project Objectives and focus on WP4 <i>Laurent Guillier</i></p>	<p>L. Guillier presented findings from a European survey on metadata used in quantitative risk assessments (QMRA) in the context of a EJP CARE Project project.</p> <p>The objective of WP4 is presented. Several questions arose delating the benchmark, the availability and quality of data commonly used for risk assessments and to describe any constraints for making them more easily accessible.</p> <p>L. Guillier presented the CARE project and showed the link with other European initiatives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- ORION: One health suRveillance Initiative on harmOnization of data collection and interpretation- COHESIVE : One Health Structure In Europe Surveillance data- RaDAR: Risk and Disease burden of Antimicrobial Resistance- NOVA: Novel approaches for design and evaluation of cost-effective surveillance across the food chain- DiSCoVer: Discovering the sources of Salmonella, Campylobacter, VTEC and antimicrobial resistance <p>The User Guide for accessing relevant data for risk-assessment that will prepare CARE partners will be presented at the EFSA MRA network at the end of 2022.</p>

C.Interactions with other JRP/JIP projects

Numerous connections were established with other JRP/JIP projects from the EJP OH consortium. Table below.

Date	Project (Persons)	Remarks
04/2020, 09/2020, 11/2020	RAKIP (DTU M. Nauta, BFR M. Filter)	Discussion on risk assessment types used in CARE
12/2020	Pathogens-in-foods (ANSES P. Kooh, IPB U. Gonzales-Barron)	This platform may host different prevalence studies (important input for QRA). The project leader are in contact with EFSA to host/transmit some relevant data for risk assessment
10/2020	JIP ORION	Attempt of the cogwheel meeting, inform them of the CARE initiative. Documents of high interest for describing with ontologies the QRA data
01/2021	EFSA	Contact to see whether EFSA's opinion should be inserted in the survey
03/2021	EJP RADAR	Exchange between CARE (RIVM) and EJP RADAR leader
09/2021	ECDC	See above
10/2021	EFSA	See above
11/2021	EJP MATRIX	Presentation of CARE activities to EJP Matrix partners during the
02/2022	EJP consortium	Presentation of CARE activities to 4th OHEJP Thematic Integrative Meeting "Data sharing across disciplines"
05/2022	EJP MATRIX	Preparation of a side-event at the ONE conference (CARE will contribute to MATRIX side-event)